

Assessment of the Patterns of Land Surface Temperature Over Ilorin, North –central Nigeria**¹Olaitan A. R. & O. O. ²Adetoro**¹Department of Geography and Environmental Management,
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Ile Ife, Nigeria.**Abstract**

This study determined the land surface temperature distribution in Ilorin town. The thermal bands 6 for Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 and thermal bands 10 and 11 for Landsat 8 respectively were processed through the model equations, where the radiance was converted to land surface temperature. The urban built-up areas recorded the highest average temperature of 27.96⁰C and 30.93⁰C in 1986 and 2015 respectively, followed by Cropland, which was 27.96⁰C and 30.93⁰C in 1986 and 2015 respectively. Savannah followed with temperatures of 26.98⁰C in 1986 and 27.42⁰C in 2015, while Water recorded temperature values of 23.75⁰C in 1986 and 27.31⁰C in 2015. The study highlights the need to intensify afforestation programs in order to mitigate climate change.

Keywords: land surface temperature, Built Up area, Cropland area, Forest area, Water bodies

Introduction

In many cities across the world, variations in land surface temperature resulting from the alteration of the ecological components of the surroundings have been a defining feature of land use patterns. A number of factors have contributed to these variations, including surface roughness, elimination of vegetative environments, and modifications to the thermal structure of physical structures (Ayanlade *et al.*, 2021). Many scholars have classified these factors responsible for intensification of land surface temperature, using the structural and land cover differences between urban and rural settings, with the former being predominantly made up of built up areas, that are characterized by rough structures, tall buildings and impervious building materials, replacing the vegetal and natural environment (Ayanlade *et al.*, 2021). In

addition to having an impact on the natural environment, changes in land use also alter the earth's radiation balance in urban areas. A greater amount of solar radiation will be absorbed during the day and re-emitted at night, if the natural features in the area are replaced with impermeable materials. Land use changes have been studied using a variety of methodologies in the past. In determining the land surface temperature, all studies done so far have employed satellite observation *et al.*, 2011).

Numerous recent studies have identified algorithms like the temperature/emissivity separation approach, the single-channel algorithm, the split-window method, and the mono-window algorithm; however, the accuracy levels vary (Jimenez and Sobrino, 2010). Therefore, the bulk of studies found that although cities continue to grow in response to population explosion, a more effective

methodical approach is required to establish significant connections between the changes in land use and the population explosion

(Nuissl and Siedentop, 2021). Thus, the purpose of this study is to evaluate Ilorin's land surface temperature using satellite data.

Methodology

The study area

Ilorin is located between latitudes 8° 24N and 8° 36N and longitudes 4° 10 E and 4°36E. It is derived guinea savannah. On the western side, Ilorin's elevation varies from 273 to 333 meters above sea level, and on the east, it ranges from 273 to 364 meters. Asa River flows from south to north, as the city's major drainage (Figure 1).

Figure 1.1c. Study area map showing the city of Ilorin

Dataset Acquisition

The long-term land surface temperature was examined in the study using a multi-year Landsat dataset, spanning 1986 to 2015. Depending on low cloud cover, the dataset covered both dry and wet seasons, and at least one month's worth of Landsat imagery. The

study evaluated changes in urban land surface temperature using the Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM), Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+), and an Operational Land Imager-Thermal Infrared Sensor (OLI-TIRS) dataset from 1986 to 2015.

Retrieval and Assessment of Land surface temperature

Ilorin's land use and land cover change were calculated with the aid of ArcMap 10.3 and ERDAS Imagine. Cropland, built-up areas, forests, and water bodies were the categories of classification for the land use and land cover change. The multi-year Landsat datasets' thermal bands were used to obtain the land surface temperature. Urban surface temperature was distinguished in the study by using thermal bands 6 (10.40–12.50 μm), 6H (10.4–12.5 μm), and 10 (10.60–11.19 μm) of TM, ETM+, and OLI-TIRS, respectively, with spatial resolutions of 120m, 60m, and 100m. These thermal bands were used to recover the urban land surface temperature, by resampling the spatial resolutions to a uniform resolution of 30m. Four major steps were involved in the data procedure: First, converting Digital Numbers (DNs) to spectral radiance; second, using Planck's inverse function to extract the urban land surface temperature; third, estimating land surface emissivity; and finally, converting the final LST values. Effective at-sensor brightness temperature, also known as black body temperature, is obtained from the spectral radiance.

The thermal bands used in this study were then extracted from the Landsat images. These bands came from the OLI Thermal Infrared Sensor, band 10 from the Thematic Mapper (TM), and band 6 from the Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+). The land surface temperature was obtained by using the split window method to retrieve the surface temperature from LANDSAT 8 OLI_TIRS and the spectral radiance model to retrieve the surface temperature from Landsat 5 TM and Landsat 7 ETM+. The spectral radiance was calculated using equation 1 while equation 2 was used to calculate the brightness temperature for band 6.

$$L = L_{\min} + (L_{\max} - L_{\min}) \times \frac{DN}{255} \quad (1)$$

$$TB = K2 / (\ln \frac{K1}{L} + 1) \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, equation 3 was used to calculate the land surface temperature for band 10 and band 11.

$$LST = TB10 + C1 (TB10 - TB11) + C2 (TB10 - TB11 + C0) + (C3 + C4W) (1 - e) + (C5 + C6W)\Delta e \quad (3)$$

Where L = Spectral Radiance, for 1986 metadata, $L_{\min} = 1.238$, $L_{\max} = 15.303$. For 2000 metadata, $L_{\min} = 0.00$, $L_{\max} = 17.00$. DN = Digital Number. Spectral Radiance (L) to Temperature in Kelvin, where LST = land surface temperature, $C0 - C6$ = split window coefficient value, $TB10$ and $TB11$ = brightness temperature of band 10 and band 11, e = mean LSE of TIRS bands, water vapor content, Δe = difference in LSE.

The value of Top Atmospheric Spectral Radiance ($TOAr$) was determined by converting original DNs and TIRS into atmospheric radiance. The original DN of Landsat 8 TIR were converted into radiance, based on the methods provided by Michael, 2003, where AL = Radiance add, ML = Radiance multiplier, DN = Digital number. The Brightness temperature (TB) for both TIR bands, where $K1$ and $K2$ = Thermal constant for TIR bands, TB = Brightness temperature; $TOAr$ = Atmospheric spectral radiance. Pearson chi-square was used to test for significant variation in temperature between 1986 and 2015, which was at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

The result showed that the average surface temperature of the study area was 26.65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the year 1986 and increased to 29.33 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 2015 (Table A.1). The result also showed that the urban heat island of: built up areas increased by 3.72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; cropland areas by 2.97 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; savannah by 0.44 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; and water by 3.56 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, between 1986 and 2015. The land use land cover classes identified recorded increase in

the surface temperature over the study period. The urban built up area recorded the highest average temperature of 27.93⁰C in 1986 and 31.65⁰C in 2015. This was followed by the cropland area at 27.96⁰C and 30.93⁰C in 1986 and 2015 respectively. The savannah area followed with the temperature of 26.98⁰C in 1986 and 27.42⁰C in 2015, while water

recorded the temperature of 23.75⁰C and 27.31⁰C in 1986 and 2015 respectively. The surface temperature for urban built up areas recorded the highest average temperature of 31.65⁰C in 2015, while water recorded the lowest temperature of 27.31⁰C from the initial 23.75⁰C of 1986 (Figure 2, Figure 3).

Figure 2: Land surface temperature distribution over Ilorin (in degree Celsius) (1986)

Figure 3: Land surface temperature distribution over Ilorin (in degree Celsius) (2015)

Table 1: Land Surface Temperature and LULCC (1986- 2015)

Land Use Classes	1986 (°C)	2015(°C)	Variability (chi square test)
Savannah	26.98	27.42	0.213 (ns)
Cropland	27.96	30.93	
Urban Built Up	27.93	31.65	
Water Bodies	23.75	27.31	
Average	26.65	29.33	

Source: Field Survey, 2017

The results further showed that there was no significant variation in the temperature difference between 1986 and 2015 at $p < 0.05$. This finding is similar to the observation by Adawa *et al.* (2022), that urban centers generally experience higher temperature than their surrounding suburbs because of reduction in vegetation covers and increase in impervious surfaces. Urban development has caused exponential decay in the urban heat island effects along the expanded rural suburbs, leading to an increase in land surface temperature at the rate of $0.12^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ from 1986 to 2015.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that the urban island formation is a result of differential increase in land surface temperature across the built up areas, cropland, and water bodies. In view of the above therefore, it is important to intensify efforts on afforestation programs in conjunction with other developmental activities. This will help to reduce the land surface temperature and also mitigate climate change.

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